

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NKENDA****FIRST NAME: ROMANUS****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID).

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: MS Word 2019 on Windows 11.

Key concepts:

1. Academic Essay Writing (EUCLID 2024, 7-14)
2. Punctuations (EUCLID 2024, 16-23)
3. American Versus British English (EUCLID, 25-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 34-39)
5. Latin Abbreviations and Expressions (EUCLID 2024, 58-62)

THE FUNDAMENTALS OF ACADEMIC PAPER WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

When I was young, my grandfather motivated me to stay in school and reminded me that education is the only way to learn how to read and write. When I could read and write, I became his secretary; I read and replied to all letters from my uncles and aunts, other family members and friends, or even the village council. Writing to me meant spelling the words correctly as instructed. Throughout my academic growth, I learned other rules, such as the use of punctuation and paragraphs. I never really understood what it meant to write an academic paper until I did my MBA. I must confess that after my MBA, I thought I knew how to write a proper academic paper until I enrolled in the EUCLID Ph.D. program, and I realized there is still so much to learn about academic writing.

I have learned that writing an excellent academic paper requires proper planning, correct grammar and punctuation, referencing materials and ideas that are not yours, and correctly citing them. I have also learned the different stages involved in academic essay writing. What differentiates academic writing from other writing is that educational writing

aims to provide answers to hypotheses through which ideas are communicated based on evidence work performed or researched.

2) ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

Writing an academic essay involves many stages, from researching the topic to submitting the final paper, journal, or thesis. As mentioned in the introduction, an academic essay's main objective is to answer questions from the hypothesis and communicate new ideas from the evidence gathered (EUCLID 2024, 7).

An excellent academic paper should be properly researched, well referenced, correctly written with correct grammar, punctuation, style, and logic, and free from plagiarism. It makes it easier for the reader to quickly capture the main ideas the paper is trying to communicate.

An excellent academic paper must have an introduction, a body, and a conclusion. The introduction moves from a general idea to a specific one, and the body builds on the concept using paragraphs and building blocks. The conclusion, however, consists of moving from a particular idea to a general one (EUCLID 2024, 10). The rule of thumb is not to introduce a new idea or concept in the conclusion.

It is essential to consider the source of information used in academic writing. Information should be backed by evidence and from reliable sources. Books, peer-reviewed journals, scholarly discussions, and online lectures from YouTube are great resources for references when writing an academic paper.

Once you finish your paper, having another person read your work is advisable to help identify errors you may have missed. This process will ensure you submit an excellent academic paper that has respected all the rules and has been adequately reviewed.

3) PUNCTUATIONS

Punctuation, to me, is the spice with which academic papers are written. Punctuations help the reader to understand the concepts presented quickly. Punctuations include commas, stops, brackets, hyphens, columns, semi-columns, inverted commas, et cetera. They must be used correctly to keep the original idea of the writer. If misused, they may distort or transmit the wrong information. It is advisable to use as little punctuation as possible. This will help keep the meaning of the sentence (EUCLID 2024, 16).

This is an example of how punctuation can mislead the reader. Consider a situation where the writer intends to say the car belongs to John.

“Its John’s car”. The correct sentence should have been, “It’s John’s car,” meaning it belongs to John.

It is paramount to ensure that punctuations are used correctly to maintain the meaning of the sentence and also to ease the reading process while grasping the message of the writer.

4) AMERICAN VERSUS BRITISH ENGLISH

I come from the English part of Cameroon, which the British colonized. Throughout my education, this was the only form of English I knew and, to me, was the only English that existed in the world. When I got into the university, I learned of the existence of American English. I realized that punctuation and spelling were different, but I was amazed at the fact the meaning remained the same. I also knew spelling was what made words mean different things. Even dates are presented differently; the British will use DD/MM/YY while the Americans will use MM/DD/YY, that is, day, month, year, and month, day, year, respectively.

EUCLID has adopted American English for essay writing. This means all work produced must make use of American English.

5) PLAGIARISM

People put in enormous amounts of work and sacrifice time and effort to produce a piece of work that has value. It is only suitable that their effort should be recognized by correctly referencing or citing their work. Plagiarism involves presenting someone else's idea or work as your own (EUCLID 2024, 34).

To avoid plagiarism, it is vital that the writer understand how to correctly cite the author or source of information from which the writer is getting the idea (EUCLID 2024, 34-35). Identifies two ways to appropriately recognize someone else's work, which are 'in-text and list works cited.' This helps the reader to see that ideas used to present your findings are not yours but are borrowed.

Plagiarism does not only kill creativity; it also endangers the future of academic writing as ideas may be misplaced, and another individual will receive credit for work that they did not do, while the actual author loses benefits that are rightly due to them. Hence, plagiarism should be avoided at all costs, not only in academic writing but in all aspects of writing.

6) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS

When writing an academic paper, one is always tempted to use abbreviations, most of which are Latin maxims. Latin abbreviations are best used in informal writing. It is advisable to use simple English for academic writing to avoid confusing the reader or sending a wrong message. (EUCLID 2024, 59).

Most commonly used are, e.g., etc., et al., and so on, which will mean in simple English, for example, and so on and other people, respectively. The writer must, therefore, ensure that words are used entirely in formal writing.

7) **CONCLUSION**

The main objective of this paper is to provide the student with the basic fundamentals of academic writing. It does this by providing rules and guidelines that must be followed to deliver a quality research paper.

Such rules consist of the different steps involved in academic writing, the various types of English used in academic writing, which are British and American English, the correct use of punctuations, how to avoid plagiarism, citing correctly, and finally, why it is essential to avoid abbreviations.

In a nutshell, this paper outlines what it takes to produce excellent academic material by following the set of rules listed above.

REFERENCES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.